

A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF LSI, NMF, LDA, AND CTM FOR VIETNAMESE SCIENTIFIC ABSTRACTS

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ABSTRACT

Topic modeling enables automatic discovery of latent themes in text corpora without manual annotation. While classical methods have proven effective across languages, Vietnamese remains understudied due to its isolating morphology. This research systematically evaluates four classical topic modeling methods—LSI, NMF, LDA, and CTM—on 8,479 Vietnamese scientific abstracts from 23 journals across six domains. Performance was assessed using Coherence (C_v), NMI, and ARI metrics through 5-fold cross-validation with three random seeds. Optimal topic numbers were determined using a weighted multi-metric framework ($0.4 \times \text{Coherence} + 0.4 \times \text{NMI} + 0.2 \times \text{ARI}$). Results demonstrate that NMF achieves superior performance at $K^=9$ (Coherence= 0.749 ± 0.004 , NMI= 0.578 ± 0.002 , ARI= 0.539 ± 0.006), outperforming CTM (0.702 ± 0.005 , 0.488 ± 0.004 , 0.423 ± 0.003 , $K^*=7$), LDA (0.601 ± 0.014 , 0.499 ± 0.004 , 0.411 ± 0.011 , $K^*=5$), and LSI (0.686 ± 0.005 , 0.373 ± 0.009 , 0.141 ± 0.006 , $K^*=3$). Notably, domain-aligned $K=6$ provides better clustering consistency for NMF (NMI= 0.625 , ARI= 0.597) with only 1.3% coherence loss, offering practical guidance for classification tasks. This study demonstrates that classical matrix factorization methods remain highly effective for Vietnamese academic texts and contributes the first large-scale benchmark dataset (VNAS) for Vietnamese topic modeling research.*

Keywords: *correlated topic model, latent Dirichlet allocation, non-negative matrix factorization, Vietnamese topic modeling.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Topic modeling represents a fundamental approach in knowledge discovery, enabling automatic identification of latent thematic structures in large document collections without manual annotation. Classical methods such as Latent Semantic Indexing (Deerwester et al., 1990), Non-negative Matrix Factorization (Lee & Seung, 1999), and Latent Dirichlet Allocation (Blei et al., 2003) have demonstrated effectiveness across multiple languages through linear algebraic decomposition, non-negative factorization, and probabilistic generative frameworks respectively. The Correlated Topic Model (Lafferty & Blei, 2005) extends LDA by modeling topic correlations, offering enhanced capability for capturing semantic relationships in interdisciplinary texts. However, the vast majority of topic modeling research focuses on English or resource-rich languages, leaving Vietnamese significantly understudied despite being spoken by over 95 million people. Vietnamese presents unique linguistic challenges as an isolating language with flexible grammar, extensive compound words, and rich contextual variation, characteristics that potentially impact classical statistical approaches differently than in morphologically rich languages. Furthermore, the application of topic modeling

to academic abstracts—typically brief, terminologically dense texts of 100-300 words—poses specific challenges for semantic extraction. Understanding which classical approaches perform optimally on Vietnamese scientific abstracts has direct implications for domestic research analytics, knowledge organization, and scholarly communication systems, motivating systematic evaluation of established methods in this understudied linguistic and domain context.

Although topic modeling is a fundamental technique in knowledge discovery, existing Vietnamese topic modeling research remains limited. Previous work has primarily focused on LDA and its variants with language-specific preprocessing techniques, such as the core terms-based approach (Thi Thu et al., 2015) and various Vietnamese NLP tools like RDRPOSTagger. However, a systematic quantitative comparison between classical algebraic methods (LSI, NMF) and probabilistic approaches (LDA, CTM) on Vietnamese scientific abstracts has not been conducted. Most comparative studies of topic modeling methods have focused on English-language social media data (Twitter, news) or e-commerce reviews, leaving the Vietnamese scholarly domain significantly understudied. Additionally, while Vietnamese linguistic features—such as isolating morphology, flexible grammar, and extensive compound words—present unique challenges for topic modeling, their impact on different algorithms' performance has not been rigorously evaluated. Furthermore, the application of these diverse methods to short, domain-specific texts like academic abstracts remains underexplored, despite this being a critical use case for knowledge discovery in academic research. Existing studies (Egger & Yu, 2022) have compared LDA, NMF, and other methods on academic abstracts, but predominantly on English-language datasets. Existing Vietnamese datasets focus primarily on news, e-commerce reviews, and educational surveys, with no large-scale benchmark dataset available for Vietnamese scientific abstracts. To address these gaps, this research systematically evaluates four classical topic modeling methods on a newly constructed dataset (VNAS) of 8,479 Vietnamese scientific abstracts from 23 journals across six research domains, assessing performance through multiple evaluation metrics (Coherence, NMI, ARI) via 5-fold cross-validation. The specific objectives are to: (1) compare quantitatively the performance of classical matrix factorization methods (LSI, NMF) against probabilistic approaches (LDA, CTM) on Vietnamese short texts, (2) employ a multi-metric evaluation framework (Zhang et al., 2022) to determine optimal topic numbers for each model, and (3) provide qualitative analysis to assess topic interpretability and practical suitability for Vietnamese scholarly text mining applications.

This study makes four key contributions to the field of Vietnamese topic modeling. First, we construct and make available a comprehensive dataset of 8,479 Vietnamese scientific abstracts collected from 23 peer-reviewed journals across six research domains (VNAS), establishing the first large-scale benchmark for Vietnamese topic modeling research that will facilitate future studies on Vietnamese scholarly text mining and knowledge discovery. Second, we provide a detailed quantitative and qualitative evaluation of four classical topic modeling approaches on Vietnamese scientific abstracts, identifying the strengths and weaknesses of matrix factorization methods (LSI, NMF) and probabilistic approaches (LDA, CTM) in the Vietnamese language context. Third, we

demonstrate that Non-negative Matrix Factorization achieves the best overall performance with Coherence of 0.749, NMI of 0.578, and ARI of 0.539, establishing it as a practical and reliable choice for Vietnamese academic text mining applications that balances interpretability with clustering accuracy. Fourth, we introduce a systematic multi-metric evaluation approach combining Coherence, NMI, and ARI to determine optimal topic numbers, providing methodological guidance for future Vietnamese NLP research and establishing best practices for topic modeling evaluation. The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 reviews the theoretical foundations of topic modeling methods and discusses related work on classical approaches, with particular emphasis on Vietnamese language applications. Section 3 presents the materials and methods, including dataset description, preprocessing pipeline, model implementations, and evaluation metrics. Section 4 reports quantitative results comparing model performance across all metrics, followed by qualitative analysis of extracted topics and their interpretability. Finally, Section 5 concludes the paper with a summary of key findings, practical recommendations for practitioners, and directions for future research.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1 Dataset Description

This study utilizes a newly constructed dataset of Vietnamese scientific abstracts (VNAS) collected from 23 peer-reviewed academic journals published in Vietnam. The dataset comprises 8,479 scientific abstracts spanning six research domains, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Distribution by Research Domain

No.	Research Domain	Number of Abstracts
1	Educational Science	1,457
2	Law	1,457
3	Medicine	1,456
4	Economics	1,451
5	Culture-Arts-Sports	1,331
6	Philosophy-Sociology-Politics	1,327
Total		8,479

The dataset construction followed a rigorous data cleaning and preprocessing pipeline. First, records with missing values or inconsistent formatting were identified and removed. Second, category labels were standardized by consolidating various journal-specific classifications into six unified research domains: Educational Science, Law, Medicine, Economics, Culture-Arts-Sports, and Philosophy-Sociology-Politics. Third, only two essential fields were retained for modeling: `abs_vi` (Vietnamese abstract text) and `label` (research domain category). Fourth, a final validation pass was conducted to verify label consistency and remove any records with incomplete or erroneous information. The resulting dataset contains 8,479 abstracts with an average length of 145 words per abstract and a total vocabulary of 41,763 unique terms. Among the 23 source

journals, 21 journals contributed 50 or more abstracts each, indicating balanced representation. The top five contributing journals were Tạp chí Nghiên cứu Y học (Medical Research Journal), Tạp chí Khoa học Thể thao (Sports Science Journal), Tạp chí Khoa học Xã hội Việt Nam (Vietnam Journal of Social Sciences), Tạp chí Thông tin KHXH (Journal of Social Sciences Information), and Tạp chí Luật học (Law Journal). This dataset distribution ensures that the topic models can be evaluated across diverse academic disciplines while maintaining statistical balance.

2.2 Text Preprocessing

The text preprocessing pipeline was designed to prepare Vietnamese scientific abstracts for topic modeling while preserving semantic information and ensuring compatibility with different model architectures. The pipeline consisted of five sequential steps:

Step 1: Tokenization and Normalization - Vietnamese word segmentation was performed using the Underthesea library, which handles the language's distinctive characteristics including compound words and multi-syllable terms. This step ensures accurate tokenization that respects Vietnamese linguistic structures, converting raw text into properly segmented word sequences.

Step 2: Stopword Removal - Two categories of stopwords were systematically removed to reduce noise and improve topic quality. The first category includes common Vietnamese function words (và, là, của, được, này, những, các, cho, từ, có) that provide grammatical structure but limited semantic value. The second category comprises domain-specific stopwords that appear frequently across all research fields (nghiên cứu, bài báo, phương pháp, kết quả, phân tích, đánh giá), which could dilute topic distinctiveness if retained.

Step 3: Dual Data Format Creation - To accommodate the requirements of different topic modeling approaches, two parallel representations of the preprocessed text were generated:

texts_clean_joined: Cleaned tokens rejoined as space-separated strings, used as input for CTM that requires continuous text

texts_tokenized: Tokens maintained as lists, used for calculating Coherence scores with Gensim's built-in evaluation functions

Step 4: Dictionary and Corpus Creation - A vocabulary dictionary was constructed using gensim.corpora.Dictionary, which maps each unique word in the corpus to a distinct numerical index. This dictionary enables the creation of bag-of-words representations required by classical topic models (LSI, NMF, LDA) and serves as the foundation for computing document-term matrices.

Step 5: Label Encoding - Research domain labels (Khoa học Giáo dục, Luật học, Y học, Kinh tế, Văn hoá - Nghệ thuật - Thể dục thể thao, Triết học - Xã hội học - Chính trị học) were transformed into numerical format using scikit-learn's LabelEncoder. This encoding is essential for calculating clustering evaluation metrics (NMI and ARI) that measure alignment between model-generated topics and ground-truth categories.

2.3 Topic Modeling Approaches

This study evaluates four topic modeling approaches spanning classical linear methods to modern neural-based techniques.

Latent Semantic Indexing (LSI): LSI employs Singular Value Decomposition (SVD) to reduce the dimensionality of the term-document matrix, revealing latent semantic structures in text (Deerwester et al., 1990). By projecting documents into a lower-dimensional space, LSI captures semantic relationships between terms, though it lacks probabilistic interpretation and may produce topics with negative values that are difficult to interpret.

Non-negative Matrix Factorization (NMF): NMF decomposes the term-document matrix into two non-negative matrices representing word-topic and topic-document distributions (Lee & Seung, 1999). The non-negativity constraint ensures additive combinations of topics, producing interpretable parts-based representations where each topic contains only positive weights, making the results more intuitive than LSI.

Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA): LDA is a generative probabilistic model that represents documents as distributions over topics, and topics as distributions over words (Blei et al., 2003). It assumes a Dirichlet prior for both document-topic and topic-word distributions, enabling coherent topic discovery through Bayesian inference. LDA has become the standard baseline for topic modeling due to its strong theoretical foundation.

Correlated Topic Model (CTM): CTM extends LDA by modeling topic correlations through a logistic-normal distribution instead of assuming topic independence (Lafferty & Blei, 2005). This allows CTM to capture relationships between topics, making it more suitable for documents where topics naturally co-occur, such as interdisciplinary scientific abstracts.

2.4 Evaluation Metrics

To comprehensively assess topic modeling performance on Vietnamese scientific abstracts, this study employs three evaluation metrics that measure both semantic coherence and alignment with ground-truth labels.

Topic Coherence (C_v) quantifies the semantic similarity between high-probability words within a topic, reflecting the interpretability and quality of discovered topics (Röder et al., 2015). This study uses C_v coherence, which combines Normalized Pointwise Mutual Information (NPMI) with cosine similarity in word embedding space:

$$C_v(t) = \frac{1}{\binom{|W_t|}{2}} \sum_{i < j} \cos(\mathbf{v}_i, \mathbf{v}_j) \cdot \text{NPMI}(w_i, w_j) \quad (1)$$

where:

$$\text{NPMI}(w_i, w_j) = \frac{\log \frac{P(w_i, w_j)}{P(w_i)P(w_j)}}{-\log P(w_i, w_j)} \quad (2)$$

Here, W_t represents the top-N words in topic t , \mathbf{v}_i and \mathbf{v}_j are word embedding vectors, and $P(w_i, w_j)$ denotes the co-occurrence probability of words w_i and w_j . Higher C_v scores indicate more coherent and interpretable topics.

NMI measures the agreement between predicted topic clusters and ground-truth labels while adjusting for chance agreement (Strehl & Ghosh, 2002). It is normalized to range $[0, 1]$, enabling fair comparison across different numbers of topics. Following (Strehl & Ghosh, 2002), NMI is computed using arithmetic mean normalization:

$$\text{NMI}(U, V) = \frac{2 \cdot I(U; V)}{H(U) + H(V)} \quad (3)$$

where $I(U; V)$ is the mutual information between clustering U and ground-truth labels V :

$$I(U; V) = \sum_{i=1}^{|U|} \sum_{j=1}^{|V|} P(i, j) \log \frac{P(i, j)}{P(i)P(j)} \quad (4)$$

and $H(U)$ and $H(V)$ are the entropies:

$$H(U) = - \sum_{i=1}^{|U|} P(i) \log P(i) \quad (5)$$

NMI = 1 indicates perfect agreement between topics and labels, while NMI ≈ 0 suggests random clustering.

ARI evaluates clustering quality by measuring the similarity between predicted and true partitions while correcting for random chance (Hubert & Arabie, 1985). It is computed as:

$$\text{ARI} = \frac{\text{RI} - \mathbb{E}[\text{RI}]}{\max(\text{RI}) - \mathbb{E}[\text{RI}]} \quad (6)$$

where RI is the Rand Index:

$$\text{RI} = \frac{a+b}{\binom{n}{2}} \quad (7)$$

Here, a is the number of document pairs in the same cluster in both predicted and true partitions, b is the number of pairs in different clusters in both partitions, and n is the total number of documents. $\mathbb{E}[\text{RI}]$ represents the expected RI under random clustering.

ARI = 1 indicates perfect clustering agreement, ARI = 0 corresponds to random clustering, and negative values indicate clustering worse than random.

To balance semantic coherence (Coherence) and label consistency (NMI, ARI), this study proposes a weighted composite metric inspired by multi-objective evaluation frameworks (Zhang et al., 2022), (Dieng et al., 2020):

$$\text{Score}_{\text{multi}}(K) = 0.4 \times \tilde{C}_v(K) + 0.4 \times \widetilde{\text{NMI}}(K) + 0.2 \times \widetilde{\text{ARI}}(K) \quad (8)$$

where each metric is normalized to $[0, 1]$ using min-max scaling:

$$\widetilde{\text{Metric}}(K) = \frac{\text{Metric}(K) - \min(\text{Metric})}{\max(\text{Metric}) - \min(\text{Metric})} \quad (9)$$

The weights (0.4, 0.4, 0.2) prioritize coherence and mutual information over ARI, as the latter is more sensitive to cluster size imbalance. The optimal number of topics K^* is selected at $\arg \max x_K \text{Score}_{\text{multi}}(K)$.

3. EXPERIENCE AND RESULTS

3.1 Experimental Setup

All experiments were conducted on a laptop computer equipped with an Intel Core i7-13620H processor (2.4 GHz, 10 cores/16 threads), 32 GB DDR5 RAM, NVIDIA RTX 4060 GPU (8 GB VRAM), and Windows 11 Home 64-bit operating system. The software environment consisted of Python 3.11 with scikit-learn 1.4 for classical models (LSI, NMF, LDA) and evaluation metrics (NMI, ARI), PyTorch 2.7 + CUDA 11.8 for GPU acceleration, Transformers 4.56 for pre-trained language models, Gensim 4.3 for coherence calculations, and tomotopy 0.12 for CTM implementation. Vietnamese-specific processing utilized Underthesea 1.3 for word segmentation, the paraphrase-multilingual-MiniLM-L12-v2 model from SentenceTransformers for contextual embeddings, and custom stopword lists containing both general Vietnamese terms (và, là, của, được, này) and domain-specific academic vocabulary (nghiên cứu, bài báo, phương pháp, kết quả). This configuration provided sufficient computational resources for processing the 8,479 Vietnamese scientific abstracts across all four classical topic modeling approaches, with GPU acceleration significantly improving training time for CTM.

Hyperparameter configuration was carefully optimized for each topic modeling approach to ensure fair comparison and optimal performance on Vietnamese scientific abstracts. For classical models (LSI, NMF, LDA, CTM), the number of topics K was systematically varied from 2 to 20 to identify the optimal configuration using the multi-metric evaluation framework. LSI employed TruncatedSVD with default parameters and TF-IDF vectorization (`max_features=5000`, `min_df=5`, `max_df=0.95`) reducing the full vocabulary of 41,763 unique terms to the 5,000 most discriminative features to balance computational efficiency with semantic coverage. NMF was configured with the coordinate descent solver (`cd`), L2 regularization (`alpha_W=0.1`, `alpha_H=0.1`), and initialized using `nndsvd` for stability. LDA utilized variational Bayes inference with a document-topic prior (`alpha=1.0/K`) and word-topic prior (`beta=0.01`), maximum iterations set to 100, and random state fixed at 42 for reproducibility. CTM combined SentenceTransformer embeddings (paraphrase-multilingual-MiniLM-L12-v2) with bag-of-words representations, using 100 training epochs, batch size of 64, and learning rate of 0.002. All models were trained with consistent preprocessing pipelines and random seeds to ensure reproducible results across multiple runs.

To ensure robust and generalizable performance evaluation, a 5-fold cross-validation strategy was implemented with multiple random seeds for all topic modeling approaches. The dataset of 8,479 Vietnamese scientific abstracts was randomly partitioned into five equal folds while maintaining balanced representation across the six research domains (Educational Science, Law, Medicine, Economics, Culture-Arts-Sports, and Philosophy-Sociology-Politics). For each fold, 80% of the data served as the training set for model fitting, while the remaining 20% was reserved for evaluation of Coherence (C_v), NMI, and ARI metrics. This process was repeated five times, with each fold serving as the test set exactly once, ensuring that every abstract was used for both training and evaluation. To account for stochastic variability in model initialization and

optimization, particularly for LDA, NMF, and CTM, three different random seeds (42, 123, 456) were employed for each fold, resulting in 15 total runs per model configuration. Final performance metrics were reported as mean \pm standard deviation across all runs, providing both central tendency and variability estimates. For all models requiring pre-specified topic numbers (LSI, NMF, LDA, CTM), this cross-validation procedure was conducted for each value of K from 2 to 20, enabling systematic identification of optimal topic counts through the multi-metric scoring framework.

3.2 Optimal Topic Number Selection

Figure 6: Topic Number (k) selection across models (coherence, NMI, ARI)

To identify the optimal number of topics for each classical model, the Multi-Metric Score framework (Equation 8) was systematically applied across K values ranging from 2 to 20. This composite metric balances semantic coherence (C_v), clustering alignment (NMI), and partition agreement (ARI) through weighted normalization, enabling objective comparison across different topic granularities. Figure 2 illustrates the variation of individual metrics (Coherence, NMI, ARI) as K increases for LSI, NMF, LDA, and CTM, revealing distinct optimization patterns for each approach. Figure 2 presents the combined Multi-Metric Score curves, where peak values indicate optimal configurations. The selection process yielded $K^*=3$ for LSI, $K^*=9$ for NMF, $K^*=5$ for LDA, and $K^*=7$ for CTM. All subsequent quantitative evaluations were conducted using these optimal topic numbers to ensure fair performance comparison across methods.

Figure 7: Optimal Topic Number (K) by Combined Multi-Metric Score

3.3 Quantitative Performance

Table 2 presents the quantitative performance of all four classical topic modeling approaches on the VNAS dataset using their optimal topic numbers, with metrics reported as mean \pm standard deviation across 5-fold cross-validation. NMF achieved the highest performance across all three metrics (Coherence=0.749, NMI=0.578, ARI=0.539), followed by CTM with stable results (Coherence=0.702, ARI=0.423). LDA demonstrated moderate performance (Coherence=0.601, NMI=0.499, ARI=0.411), while LSI showed relatively high Coherence (0.686) but poor label alignment (ARI=0.141).

Table 2: Performance Metrics of Topic Models on VNAS Dataset

Model	Coherence (C_v)	NMI	ARI	K^*
LSI	0.686 \pm 0.005	0.373 \pm 0.009	0.141 \pm 0.006	3
NMF	0.749 \pm 0.004	0.578 \pm 0.002	0.539 \pm 0.006	9
LDA	0.601 \pm 0.014	0.499 \pm 0.004	0.411 \pm 0.011	5
CTM	0.702 \pm 0.005	0.488 \pm 0.004	0.423 \pm 0.003	7

Note: All metrics reported as mean \pm standard deviation across 5-fold cross-validation with 3 random seeds (15 runs total). K^* denotes the optimal number of topics determined by Multi-Metric Score.

3.4 Comparison with Domain-Aligned Topic Number

To validate whether the automatically determined optimal topic numbers truly represent the best configuration for domain classification tasks, we conducted an additional experiment by fixing $K=6$ for all models to match the actual number of research

domains in the VNAS dataset. This comparison addresses a practical question frequently encountered in supervised text mining applications: should topic numbers be selected through optimization metrics or aligned with known domain structures?

Table 3 presents the performance metrics when all four classical methods are constrained to $K=6$ topics, evaluated using the same 5-fold cross-validation procedure with three random seeds (15 runs total). Results are reported as mean \pm standard deviation.

Table 3: Performance Metrics at Domain-Aligned Topic Number ($K=6$)

Model	Coherence (C_v)	NMI	ARI
LSI	0.667 \pm 0.010	0.408 \pm 0.010	0.152 \pm 0.007
NMF	0.739 \pm 0.002	0.625 \pm 0.001	0.597 \pm 0.003
LDA	0.598 \pm 0.004	0.481 \pm 0.009	0.394 \pm 0.003
CTM	0.682 \pm 0.029	0.474 \pm 0.019	0.409 \pm 0.028

Figure 3: Top Words Extracted by Topic Models

4. DISCUSSION

The quantitative results reveal significant performance differences across the four classical topic modeling approaches on Vietnamese scientific abstracts. NMF achieves superior overall performance with Coherence of 0.749, NMI of 0.578, and ARI of 0.539 at $K=9$, establishing it as the optimal choice for Vietnamese academic text mining. The non-negativity constraint of NMF produces interpretable additive combinations of topics,

enabling clearer semantic separation of research domains compared to probabilistic alternatives. CTM demonstrates stable intermediate performance (Coherence=0.702, ARI=0.423, K=7) through explicit modeling of topic correlations via logistic-normal distributions (Lafferty & Blei, 2005). This advantage proves particularly valuable for interdisciplinary scientific abstracts where semantic overlap between domains is inevitable. However, CTM's higher computational cost and sensitivity to embedding quality limit its practical applicability compared to NMF. LDA exhibits moderate performance (Coherence=0.601, NMI=0.499, K=5) despite being the standard baseline in topic modeling (Blei et al., 2003). Its lower coherence reflects challenges in capturing semantic relationships within short, terminologically dense abstracts. LSI serves as a baseline with acceptable coherence (0.686) but poor label alignment (ARI=0.141), confirming limitations of linear projection methods (Deerwester et al., 1990) for Vietnamese domain discrimination.

The comparison between domain-aligned (K=6) and optimization-driven (K star equals 9) topic numbers reveals a critical practical trade-off. While the multi-metric optimization framework selected K star equals 9 for NMF by prioritizing Coherence (weight equals 0.4), fixing K equals 6 to match the six research domains yields substantially better clustering alignment with minimal coherence loss. Specifically, NMF at K equals 6 achieves NMI of 0.625 and ARI of 0.597, representing improvements of 8.1% and 10.8% respectively over K star equals 9, while Coherence decreases only 1.3% from 0.749 to 0.739. This finding suggests that when ground-truth domain structure is known, domain-aligned topic numbers provide superior clustering consistency for classification tasks, whereas optimization-driven selection maximizes semantic granularity for exploratory analysis.

The strong performance of matrix factorization methods reflects Vietnamese linguistic characteristics. The isolating morphology and minimal morphological variation create relatively stable term-topic associations amenable to algebraic decomposition (Lee & Seung, 1999). Compound words and specialized terminology, while challenging for general embeddings, are effectively handled by NMF's explicit term weighting mechanism through TF-IDF preprocessing with Underthesea tokenization effectively handles compound words and specialized terminology through explicit term weighting. The modest performance difference between CTM and NMF suggests that Vietnamese abstracts maintain relatively discrete domain boundaries.

For Vietnamese academic text mining applications, the results support a pragmatic tiered recommendation. When ground-truth domains are known, using K equal to the number of domains (e.g., K equals 6 for VNAS) is recommended for classification tasks to maximize clustering consistency. First, NMF is recommended for resource-constrained applications requiring interpretability and computational efficiency, as it consistently delivers superior performance across all evaluation metrics while maintaining fast training times and minimal hyperparameter tuning. Second, CTM is suitable for interdisciplinary research synthesis requiring topic relationship analysis, particularly when computational resources permit longer training times and when understanding topic correlations provides additional analytical value. Third, LDA remains viable as a baseline

probabilistic approach when Bayesian inference properties are theoretically desirable, though its performance on short Vietnamese texts suggests limited practical advantage over NMF. Fourth, LSI should be reserved for preliminary exploratory analysis or dimensionality reduction tasks rather than primary topic modeling objectives, given its poor clustering alignment despite reasonable coherence scores.

The implications for Vietnamese NLP research extend beyond topic modeling. The success of classical algebraic methods on Vietnamese text suggests that morphologically simple, isolating languages may not uniformly benefit from the complexity of modern neural architectures, particularly in low-resource or domain-specific contexts. The effectiveness of TF-IDF preprocessing combined with language-specific tokenization (Underthesea) demonstrates that careful linguistic preprocessing can compensate for the absence of language-specific pre-trained models. Future work should investigate whether similar patterns hold for other isolating languages in the Austroasiatic family, and whether domain-specific Vietnamese embeddings could improve CTM performance to surpass NMF's current advantage.

5. CONCLUSION

This study provides the first systematic quantitative comparison of classical topic modeling approaches (LSI, NMF, LDA, CTM) on Vietnamese scientific abstracts. Using 8,479 abstracts from 23 journals across six domains, we demonstrate that NMF achieves superior performance across all evaluation metrics (Coherence equals 0.749, NMI equals 0.578, ARI equals 0.539). The research contributes: (1) the VNAS benchmark dataset for Vietnamese topic modeling research, (2) a systematic multi-metric evaluation framework combining Coherence, NMI, and ARI, and (3) empirical evidence that classical matrix factorization remains highly competitive for short Vietnamese texts. Importantly, our analysis reveals that domain-aligned topic numbers (K equals 6) provide 8 to 11% improvement in clustering metrics (NMI, ARI) compared to optimization-driven selection (K star equals 9), with minimal coherence trade-off (1.3% decrease). This finding offers practical guidance: use K equal to the number of domains for classification applications prioritizing domain alignment, and optimization-driven K star for exploratory analysis maximizing semantic granularity.

Despite these contributions, several important limitations constrain the generalizability of findings. First, this study focused exclusively on four classical methods and did not evaluate modern neural approaches such as BERTopic (Grootendorst, 2022) or Top2Vec (Angelov, 2020), limiting understanding of the full landscape of topic modeling performance on Vietnamese texts. Second, the CTM implementation relied on multilingual embeddings (paraphrase-multilingual-MiniLM-L12-v2) rather than Vietnamese-specific pre-trained models such as PhoBERT (Nguyen & Nguyen, 2020), which may have artificially constrained performance. Third, the analysis was restricted to short scientific abstracts (average 145 words), preventing assessment of whether classical methods maintain advantages on longer documents where contextual information becomes more important. Fourth, the single-language focus on

Vietnamese prevents cross-linguistic generalization, and fifth, all classical methods rely on bag-of-words representations that discard word order and contextual semantics.

Future research should pursue three critical directions. First and most importantly, systematic evaluation of neural topic modeling approaches, particularly BERTopic and Top2Vec, using Vietnamese-specific pre-trained embeddings such as PhoBERT or vELECTRA trained on domain-specific Vietnamese academic corpora is essential to determine whether classical methods' advantage stems from algorithmic characteristics or from inadequacy of multilingual embeddings—if Vietnamese-optimized embeddings substantially improve neural performance, BERTopic could potentially surpass NMF's current benchmark. Second, extension to full-length Vietnamese academic papers and dissertations would reveal whether classical methods maintain advantages on longer texts or if neural approaches benefit more from increased contextual information. Third, development of hybrid models combining classical matrix factorization interpretability with Vietnamese embedding semantic richness could offer superior performance. As Vietnamese-specific language models mature, neural approaches like BERTopic warrant systematic re-evaluation and may emerge as superior alternatives for Vietnamese scholarly text mining. The VNAS dataset and evaluation framework provide the necessary infrastructure for rigorous assessment of future methods.

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